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The Experience of the Love for Children in Teaching

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Abstract

This research explores into the experiences of teachers in Department of Education public schools, focusing on their demonstration of "love for children" in the teaching environment. It employs an auto-ethnographic qualitative research design, involving three current Department of Education employees in SOCCSKSARGEN. Four themes emerged from the participants' shared experiences: service of love, presence, positive discipline, and belief in the young. The "service of love" theme highlights teachers' commitment to providing exceptional support and nurturing environments for children. "Presence" underscores the importance of teachers being fully engaged and emotionally invested, creating a valued and safe atmosphere. "Positive discipline" emphasizes constructive and empathetic methods to guide behavior, maintaining dignity and self-esteem. Lastly, "belief in the young" recognizes every child's potential, with teachers nurturing and encouraging it. This study offers profound insights into loving children in teaching, emphasizing love as service, being fully present, using positive discipline, and unwavering belief in every child's potential. These insights can enhance academic learning and holistic development, with implications for teaching philosophy and practice in public education.

Keywords: *love for children, teaching, positive discipline, public education, education*

Introduction

At the heart of Saint Marcellin Champagnat's educational philosophy was the holistic development of children. The Marist Brothers' schools emphasized character formation, nurturing both the intellectual and moral growth of students. Saint Marcellin believed that education should not only prepare children for a successful life but also instill in them a sense of purpose, empathy, and a deep-rooted faith. His approach was marked by love, care, and an unwavering commitment to the well-being of his students. One of the virtues of St. Marcellin Champagnat is the love for children. He believed that it is also important to educate children not just about faith but to educate them as well of their surrounding and themselves.

St. Marcellin Champagnat's love for children is clearly manifested on the existence of Marist Brothers who are offering Marist Education. The foundational qualities of Marist Pedagogy include presence and good example, ease of relationship between teacher and student, preference for simplicity, new and more effective methods in learning, importance of the craft of teaching, belief in the young and active awareness of the presence of God.

Teaching is a noble profession that requires educators to not only impart knowledge but also foster a nurturing environment in which children can thrive emotionally, socially, and academically. In the context of public education, it is important to know what it means to love the children. There are few research that tackles how teachers show their love to their students in the classroom. The experiences of teachers in this concept vary as they have their own way of showing love to their students. The love and care that teachers extend to their students play a pivotal role in their development. This view is in agreement to the study of Dennis (2012) stipulating that the presence of love in the classroom makes a teacher effective, thus, improves the performance of the students.

Teachers in the Department of Education in public schools express their love in various ways within their classroom. By providing activities that address the different learning styles of the students. Teachers also show their encouragement and support to their students through words of affirmation and celebration of achievements, fostering a nurturing environment where every child feels valued and accepted. Teachers also go beyond their duty by providing extra help and support to their students.

However, there are some circumstances that some educators find difficult to perform due to the different roles at hand. Teachers often face numerous challenges that can hinder their ability to express genuine love and affection for their students. Some problems that teachers experienced are more workloads, large class sizes, diverse students' needs, and students' behavioral challenges. Aside from these, teachers are also bound by some laws governing the discipline of children and personal concerns at home.

On this premise, this study is to be conducted with the hope of finding out how teachers in the public schools of the Department of Education experienced the love for children. Particularly, it is the intention of the researchers to discover how the research-participant manifest love for children at school, their experiences in loving children at school, and the things they do that manifest love for children.

Research Questions

The study aimed to describe how the researcher-participants experienced the "love for children" in teaching in the context of the Department of Education (DepEd) public Schools.

Methodology

The study employed auto-ethnographic qualitative research design. Autoethnography is an approach to research and writing that seeks to describe and systematically analyze personal experience in order to understand cultural experience (Ellis et. Al., 2011). This research design was used to explore the experiences of the participants on the love for children in teaching. The study involved three (3) research-participants who are currently employed to the Department of Education within SOCCSKSARGEN. These participants are from different school division offices handling different grade levels. Guided with the research question, the research-participants shared their experiences of the love for children in teaching through in-depth interview using the Key Informant Interview Guide. The results were then subjected to Coding and Thematic Analysis where various themes were created.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the discussion of the result based on the experiences of the Department of Education teachers on the love for children in teaching. Based on the shared experiences of the three research – participants, there were four themes which emerged from their shared experiences – service of love, presence, positive discipline and belief in the young.

<i>Text Segments</i>	<i>Code/ Participants</i>	<i>Concepts</i>	<i>Themes</i>
Doing home-visitation of SARDO beyond office hours and listening to their stories and reasons is rewarding especially when you were able to save them from dropping out of school	P1	Understanding present needs of students	Service of love
At times, you need to take out money from your own pocket just to provide the needs of your students. As experienced, I used to have adopted students before where I am the one paying for their PTA and HRPTA Projects as well as any contributions in our school. I also support the project of the school where my co-teacher and I provided a bicycle to one of our chosen students. This bicycle served as the transportation of the said student to go to school.	P2	Providing the needs	
Most of the time, I gave the needs of my students most especially the important ones. I experienced giving them papers, pencils, ballpens and foods at times. I always believe in whatever they can do and make sure that while they are in school, I do my best to bring out the best in them. There are some learners who came to school with an empty stomach and who can even listen well to the teachers kung naga pamati ka man sang huni sang tyan mo? That's why I sometimes offer food to eat.	P3	Provision of needs	
Spending time with my students during recess time and noon break and listening to their life updates makes them more comfortable with me and thus leads to trust and confidence that I will listen to them	P1	Giving time to students in order build trust and confidence	Presence
I love bonding with my students during my free time, either lunch breaks or after dismissal in the afternoon where I used to wait for my husband to fetch me. While waiting, we laughed at stories which we share with each other, and share different stories. Through spending time with them, you will soon discover that the school is where they can be themselves and for some it is a place where they find comfort and joy while being with other students. I feel happy when I get to listen to different stories of my students. It also made me discover that these students also need our attention and they only wanted someone whom they can share their thoughts and who will listen to them.	P2	Bonding with the students	
Whenever I am not around at school due to seminars outside or sports competitions, I always hear from my students these questions, “Nay kelan ka babalik?”...”Nay, saan ka?”....As if the classroom is dull without my presence. The moment I will return to school, they will swarm at my table, telling me how much they missed me and they will share stories which I missed from being away. I also enjoy my time being with my students.	P2	Being there for the students	
Ginatutukan gid Sila. I always make sure that they are well taken cared of. I make sure that they are learning. There are times that I will talk to them one by one. Teaching them one by one. However, it's also saddening that there are times that I cannot cater all of them because of time constraint. I feel sorry for those who cannot be accommodated. But, I make sure nga mabatyagan gid nila nga Ara ko for them.	P3		
I would prefer reprimand students rather than tolerate wrongdoings. I always remind myself not to be tired on reminding them regarding school rules and values. In this way I can show them that I am concerned for them and thus developing them to be better persons is my mission.	P1	Disciplining students out of love	Positive Discipline

I also make sure that the wrongdoings of my students are not being tolerated. I always remind them about the rules being implemented in the school and the importance of obeying these rules because they can apply it even in real life.	P2		
I reprimand. It's not all the time nga pirimi ka buot sa ila in a way nga you will let them do whatever they want to do. I also make sure that they will get reprimanded when they did something wrong. I explain to them that I am not mad at them but I am mad with their actions. As a teacher, Gina sigurado ko gid na I will be the father figure in the school who will not tolerate their wrong doings because what I am doing is for them.	P3		
I had once a student who for the 3rd time was enrolled in the same grade level, he went to me and ask if I can cater him in my advisory class (1st section class) with his hope that I can help him. I gave him a chance believing that he too can change to a better one. Truly, he eventually changed his attitude towards schooling and often share his struggles on me. He would always claim, "magtinarong ko kay palangga ko ni maam".	P1	Caring for the students	Belief in the Young
I always encourage my students to believe in themselves and I always remind them that each one of them is endowed with talents and skills, that everybody is unique in their own ways.	P2		
Encouraging them. When they achieved something, I am the proudest as their teacher. I always encourage them to do better, to be great. I challenge them to excel kag maningkamot gid sa pag eskwela Kay para gid na sa ila kag ila pamilya. I always recognize their good deeds and applaud them.	P3		

One of the themes which emerged from the discussion of the research-participants is the service of love. Based on the experiences of the three research – participants, all of them experienced extending their service to their students out of their love for them. Paulo Freire, one of the intellectuals on love who is frequently mentioned, asserts with confidence that "it is impossible to teach without the courage to love." as cited by Kaukko et al. (2022). As one participant mentioned, "Doing home-visitation of SARDO beyond office hours and listening to their stories and reasons is rewarding especially when you were able to save them from dropping out of school". This experience is a manifestation that a teacher extends services beyond office hours because of his love for students. Conducting home visitation even beyond office hours can be perceived as an act that a teacher voluntarily does because of his love for his students.

Another research-participant revealed that at times, she need to take out money from your own pocket just to provide the needs of your students. The same experience was claimed by another research-participant who said, " Most of the time, I gave the needs of my students most especially the important ones. I experienced giving them papers, pencils, ballpens and foods at times.". This supports the study of Kaukko et al. (2022), which mentioned that the teachers' willingness to make sacrifices in the name of love implies that they are motivated to meet the needs of their students.

The theme service of love can be perceived as acts done by the teacher apart from his teaching job which focuses only on his subject taught. This service of love are manifested by research-participants through willingness to do tasks beyond office hours and the generosity to share resources in order to see to it that school children are kept in school.

Another theme which emerged from the responses of the research – participants is Presence. The availability of teacher to be with students during break time is a clear manifestation of presence. Both Participants 1 and 2 shared that they spend time with their students where students will update them with the things that are happening in their lives. Through this, they can build trust among the students and at the same bond with them.

Participant 3 shared that "Ginatutukan gid Sila. I always make sure that they are well taken cared of. I make sure that they are learning. There are times that I will talk to them one by one. Teaching them one by one. However, it's also saddening that there are times that I cannot cater all of them because of time constraint. I feel sorry for those who cannot be accommodated. But, I make sure nga mabatyan gid nila nga Ara ko for them."

This supports the study of Dennis (2012), which revealed that we must get to know each student on an individual basis, as well as their family, in order to show them our affection. This can be accomplished by having conversations with students, sharing stories, and sharing personal experiences. It can also be accomplished by looking at family photos that students have brought to class. The rapport between educators and learners was strengthened by these programs.

On the other hand, in the nurturing arms of positive discipline, children discover the profound significance of responsibility, respect, and self-regulation. Disciplining students out of love plays a very vital role in the teaching process. Participant 3 mentioned, "I also make sure that they will get reprimanded when they did something wrong. I explain to them that I am not mad at them but I am mad with their actions". Reprimanding the students for their wrong actions shows that the teacher loves them. As the second parent when they are in school, it is the teacher who will really make sure that they are safe while learning. He even further explained, "As a teacher, Gina sigurado ko gid na I will be the father figure in the school who will not tolerate their wrong doings because what I am doing is for them". Similarly, participant 3 agrees that students should be reprimanded rather than tolerate them for wrong actions. She reason-

out that “In this way I can show them that I am concerned for them and thus developing them to be better persons is my mission”. She believes that through positive discipline, students would be able to feel the love for them because these actions are not just for the teachers but as well as for the common good. Same is true with the response of Participant 2 that “I always remind them about the rules being implemented in the school and the importance of obeying these rules because they can apply it even in real life.” She also believes that students should learn to become law-abiding persons since they can apply it in real life.

In the study of Tartari (2018), it was found that positive relationship positively affects the academic achievements of the students. Consequently, it is suggested that teachers should create a positive climate of cooperation in the classroom by practicing as many elements of positive discipline, because this relationship increases the level of student learning by influencing their education with values and positive principles for a healthier society. As mentioned by Zakrzewski (2012), a caring teacher can transform the school experience especially for students who face enormous difficulties, such as dropping out or dysfunctional home lives.

The last theme which emerged from the study is belief in the young. Participant 1 shared that she had a student who was a Balik-Aral. The student begged her to admit him in her class. Participant 1 mentioned “I gave him a chance believing that he too can change to a better one. Truly, he eventually changed his attitude towards schooling and often share his struggles on me. He would always claim, "magtinarong ko kay palangga ko ni maam". Indeed, giving the students second chances to reform themselves may somehow has a positive effect on them.

Participant 2 also shared that “I always encourage my students to believe in themselves and I always remind them that each one of them is endowed with talents and skills, that everybody is unique in their own ways”, students need encouragement at times and .it will also have an impact on how they behave in the classroom when they feel that there is someone who cares for them.

Participant 3 shared also that he encourage his students. When the students achieved something, he feels proud for their achievement. He explained that, “I always encourage them to do better, to be great. I challenge them to excel kag maningkamot gid sa pag eskwela Kay para gid na sa ila kag ila pamilya. I always recognize their good deeds and applaud them.” Students need to feel that someone is believing in them and it can also help and motivate them to do good in their classes.

This is in consonance with Dennis (2012) who stipulated in her study that without love, children would probably perform poorly in the classroom, where love is a necessary ingredient for an effective teacher.

Conclusions

This study aimed to describe how the researcher-participants experienced the “love for children” in teaching in the context of the Department of Education (DepEd) public Schools.

The concept of loving children in the context of teaching is a profound and multifaceted theme. Based on the experiences shared by the researcher – participants, loving children in the context of teaching is based on service of love, presence, positive discipline, and belief in the young.

First, "service of love" gives us the idea that teachers should approach their role as an act of love and care towards their students. This means going above and beyond in terms of providing support, guidance, and a nurturing environment for children to thrive. It recognizes that love, in this context, is not just an emotion but a dedicated commitment to the well-being and development of each child.

Second, the importance of "presence" highlights the significance of being fully engaged and emotionally invested in the teaching process. When teachers are present, not only physically but also mentally and emotionally, they create an atmosphere where children feel valued, understood, and safe. This emotional connection and attentiveness contribute to the overall learning experience, fostering trust and a sense of security, which are essential for a child's development.

"Positive discipline" is another crucial aspect of teaching with love. It emphasizes the use of constructive and empathetic methods to guide and manage children's behavior, rather than resorting to punitive measures. This approach teaches students important life skills, such as problem-solving and self-regulation, while maintaining their dignity and self-esteem.

Lastly, the "belief in the young" recognizes that every child has potential, and it is the teacher's role to nurture and encourage this potential. When teachers have faith in the capabilities of their students, it can significantly boost children's self-esteem and motivation. It fosters a growth mindset and a sense of self-worth, contributing to a positive and empowering educational experience.

These four themes offer profound insights into the concept of loving children in the context of teaching. They underscore the importance of love as a service, being fully present in the teaching process, using positive discipline, and having unwavering belief in the potential of every child. By incorporating these insights into their teaching philosophy, teachers can create an environment that not only enhances academic learning but also nurtures the holistic development of young minds.

Implications

It can be noted that Dennis (2012) mentioned that t little research has been done on how teachers demonstrate love in the classroom. In his study, looked into how five classroom teachers described their lives in relation to their careers and how they exhibited love to

their students.

In this study, the results highlighted the four key themes of loving children in the context of teaching—service of love, presence, positive discipline, and belief in the young—carry significant implications for both teachers and educational institutions. First, these findings emphasize how teachers experience the love for children in teaching apart from seeing teaching as mere profession. Teachers should be seen not only as purveyors of knowledge but as caretakers of young minds, guiding and nurturing them with a genuine "service of love." This implies that educational systems should place a higher value on teachers who not only possess subject matter expertise but also exhibit qualities of empathy, compassion, and a deep commitment to their students' well-being.

Additionally, these themes underscore the importance of fostering a positive, supportive, and empathetic learning environment within schools. Schools should prioritize creating an atmosphere where "presence" is valued, ensuring that teachers are not only physically present but emotionally engaged with their students. This implies a need for smaller class sizes, manageable workloads for educators, and an emphasis on teacher-student relationships. It also implies the need for schools to implement and support "positive discipline" strategies that prioritize the well-being and character development of students, promoting a culture of mutual respect and responsibility. Furthermore, fostering "belief in the young" requires schools to create an environment that encourages individual growth, self-confidence, and a focus on the potential of every student. Ultimately, the implications of these themes call for a reevaluation of educational priorities and practices, emphasizing the holistic development and well-being of children within the learning process.

It can be implied that St. Marcellin Champagnat's love and care for children were also manifested by teachers in Department of Education as discussed in their different experiences of love for children in teaching. By modeling his beliefs and values, teachers may foster a climate where kids feel loved, valued, and empowered to realize their greatest potential. It can be viewed that St. Marcellin Champagnat's legacy continues to inspire educators.

It is also implied that this study is limited to the experiences of three teachers in Department of Education within SOCCSKSARGEN who happened to be the research-participants of this study. Thus, further research studies on how teachers experience the love for children in teaching is highly encouraged to uncover more actual teachers' experiences in the context of the teaching profession as well as the challenges in loving children within schools.

References

Barmi, B. (2023). Importance of affection in teaching younger children

Dennis, Mary (2012). "A study of how teachers show love in the classroom". Doctor of Education (EdD). 13. <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/edd/13>

Ellis, Adams & Bochner (2011). Autoethnography: An Overview

Kaukko, M., Wilkinson, J., & Kohli, R. K. (2022). Pedagogical love in Finland and Australia: A study of refugee children and their teachers. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 30(5), 731-747. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2020.1868555>

Vanderheiden, Elisabeth (2023) 'I could never think of education without love' - Pedagogical love in the context of adult education, *International Review of Psychiatry*, 35:1, 62-85, DOI: 10.1080/09540261.2023.2172999

Zakrzewski, V. (2012, September 18). Four Ways Teachers Can Show They Care. *Greater Good Magazine Science-Based Insights for a Meaningful Life*. Retrieved from https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/article/item/caring_teacher_student_relationship

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